

STITCHING EFFECT FOR INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CFRP LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: DCB (Double Cantilever Beam) and ENF (End Notched Flexure) tests have been conducted for through-thickness stitched CFRP specimens made by RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) process to predict the effect of stitching on the Mode I (G_{IR}) and Mode II (G_{IIR}) interlaminar fracture toughness. In this study, stitching parameters (e.g. the stitch density and thickness of a stitch thread) have been varied. The dry performs have been stitched with each stitching parameter before the injection and cure process of the epoxy resin (TORAY TR-A31^B). The Mode I strain energy release rate G_{IR} values have been obtained from DCB tests and it is concluded that the G_{IR} values are proportional to the stitch density and the thickness of the stitch threads affects the slopes of the regression lines. On the other hand, the Mode II strain energy release rate G_{IIR} values have been obtained from ENF tests. However, it is confirmed that ENF method may not be suitable to obtain the G_{IIR} values in stitched composites.

KEYWORDS: stitching, interlaminar fracture toughness, DCB (Double Cantilever Beam), ENF (End Notched Flexure), RTM (Resin Transfer Molding)

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have many advantages (e.g. the high specific strength, the high specific modulus) and are now used widely in a variety of applications. However, these materials, especially traditional 2-D composite laminates, generally exhibit poor interlaminar fracture toughness and thus are susceptible to delamination when subjected to interlaminar stresses. In some applications of composite materials to aircraft structures, this poor property may cause the deterioration of the CAI (Compression After Impact) strength, OHC (Open Hole Compression) strength...etc., and for buckled skin panels may affect the resistance of interlaminar peel loads at interfaces of skin-stringer structure. For these reasons, the improvement of composite laminates' interlaminar fracture toughness gives a possibility to more lightweight structures by damage tolerance or post buckling designs. Up to now, various techniques to improve this poor property have been introduced, especially the employment of stitching and 3-D fabric with low cost consolidation techniques such as RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) or RFI (Resin Film Infusion) have been evaluated in several countries. In Japan in 1980's, National Aerospace Laboratory reported an evaluation of stitched CFRP laminates manufactured by stitched prepreg / autoclave consolidation [1]. It was confirmed that stitching gave a possibility of crack arresting and to postpone final fracture under static loads. On the other hand, disadvantages were reported such as a decrease in bending and in-plane strength. The reason for the lower strength was that stitch needle gave damages to carbon fiber (CF) bundles in prepreg or voids were formed at through-thickness thread's holes. Recently, however, the improvement of RTM or RFI techniques, which are applicable to dry preform consolidation systems, have been helped to reduced the damages of CF bundles by stitching. The authors' group has carried out re-evaluations of stitched CFRP specimens manufactured by RTM process including the static strength, CAI [2], fatigue [3] and Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IR} [4, 5]. To date, we have obtained and evaluated only the G_{IR} values of interlaminar fracture toughness. The goal of this work is to evaluate the effect of stitching on the G_{IIR} values in addition to that of the G_{IR} values.

EXPERIMENTAL

Stitching process: Stitching is usually performed by sewing machines. Conventional stitching machines are equipped with one needle, where needle and bobbin threads are supplied to preforms from both sides. In this process, the stitch line corresponds with the stitching direction and through-thickness fibers are stitched normal to the plane of preforms. A Schematic diagram of a conventional stitching process is shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 shows the aspects of both surfaces on stitched preforms.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of a conventional stitching

Figure 2. Aspects of both surfaces on preforms

RTM process: The cure cycle of TORAY TR-A31^B employed here is shown in Fig. 3. During a resin transfer process, the resin transfer pump at the inlet of the mold pressurized resin and the vacuum pump at the outlet of it drew resin.

Figure 3. Cure cycle

Test specimen: Fig. 4 illustrates the configurations and dimensions of the DCB and ENF specimens employed here respectively. Before epoxy resin (TORAY TR-A31^B) impregnation, plain woven sheets of CF have been 20-ply-stacked and stitched with Kevlar[®] threads along the length as shown in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively, where the stitch density and thickness of a thread have been varied. Although these specimens are intended to have designed stitch densities with the particular pitch and space, each specimen has individual stitch parameters in terms of stitching or trimming conditions. The stitch densities, therefore, have been measured for each specimen after the tests. Furthermore, unidirectional CFRP tabs are bonded on the top and bottom of test specimens because stitched test specimens require the high bending strength caused by the high interlaminar fracture toughness when a crack propagates. These tabs can relieve the bending stress and avoid the failure of specimen arms before the crack propagation.

Figure 4. Configurations of DCB and ENF Specimen

Table 1. Specification of stitching parameters on DCB specimen

Series	Thickness [tex]	Fracture Load [N]	Twist	Stitch Density [$/\text{mm}^2$]
<i>A</i>	44	78	22 tex*2	0-0.100
<i>B</i>	66	117	22 tex*3	0-0.022
<i>C</i>	88	156	22 tex*4	0-0.077

Table 2. Specification of stitching parameters on ENF specimen

Series	Thickness [tex]	Fracture Load [N]	Twist	Stitch Density [$/\text{mm}^2$]
<i>a</i>	44	78	22 tex*2	0-0.103
<i>b</i>	66	117	22 tex*3	0-0.088
<i>c</i>	88	156	22 tex*4	0-0.089

Test procedures: DCB tests are conducted for the stitched specimens with various stitching parameters under displacement-controlled mode and a constant displacement rate of 0.25 mm/min, where insert type loading fixture [6] developed at National Aerospace laboratory of Japan is used. The crack length is measured at both specimen sides by the microscope when crack propagation is observed. A picture of DCB tests is shown in Fig. 5. In this case, several failed stitch threads are observed.

Figure 5. Picture of DCB Tests

Figure 6. Picture of ENF Tests

A picture of ENF tests is shown in Fig. 6. The tests are conducted for the stitched specimens under a constant displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. The measurement system of the crack length is the same as that of DCB tests. During the tests, the aluminum plate is set on the each specimen so that it might prevent UD CFRP Tab being failed at loading point by stress concentration before crack propagation in terms of the high interlaminar fracture toughness of the specimens.

Calculations of the G_{IR} and G_{IIR} : A typical load-COD (Crack Opening Displacement) curve obtained from DCB tests is shown in Fig. 7 and a typical load-deflection curve obtained from ENF tests is shown in Fig. 8 to explain area methods for the G_{IR} and G_{IIR} calculation respectively.

The equations for the G_{IR} calculation are as follows:

$$G_{IRi} = \frac{dU_i}{dA_i} = \frac{dU_i}{b \times dC_i} \quad (1)$$

$$\overline{G_{IR}} = G_{IR} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{G_{IRi}}{n} \quad (2)$$

where b is the width of the each specimen, dC_i is a crack growth length and therefore dA_i is the area of a delamination.

□

Figure 7. Area Method for G_{IR} calculation

Figure 8. Area Method for G_{IIR} calculation

And the equations for the G_{IR} calculation are as follows:

$$G_{IRi} = \frac{dU_i}{dA_i} = \frac{dU_i}{b \times dC_i} \quad (3)$$

$$\overline{G_{IR}} = G_{IR} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{G_{IRi}}{n} \quad (4)$$

where b and dC_i are the same as the variable of eq. (1). As mentioned later, the data scatter and other problems of ENF test are considered when the G_{IR} calculation is performed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Typical load-COD curves for DCB specimens: Typical load-COD curves for series *A* are shown in Fig. 9(a) to (d). Notice that the specimen with the higher stitch density has the larger area of the strain energy and slower crack propagation. This tendency has been obtained from all series of the specimens.

Figure 9. Typical load-COD curves for (a) an unstitched specimen, (b) a specimen stitched with the density of $0.019/\text{mm}^2$, (c) a specimen stitched with the density of $0.034/\text{mm}^2$, (d) a specimen stitched with the density of $0.1/\text{mm}^2$.

R-curves for DCB specimens: Figure 10 shows the R-curves for the identical specimens in Fig. 9(a) to (d). It is obvious that the stitched specimens produce a significant improvement in the G_{IR} value in terms of increasing stitch density. Furthermore, in this work, the G_{IR} values don't increase with increasing crack length, and they are almost constant. The same tendency was found for the other specimens, therefore, the G_{IR} values are calculated by eq. (1) and eq. (2).

Figure 10. R-curves for (a) an unstitched specimen, (b) a specimen stitched with the density of $0.019/\text{mm}^2$, (c) a specimen stitched with the density of $0.034/\text{mm}^2$, (d) a specimen stitched with the density of $0.1/\text{mm}^2$.

G_{IR} -stitch density plots: Figure 11 shows the G_{IR} -stitch density plots for the all series of the specimens. Notice that the G_{IR} values of each series increase with increasing stitch density. Moreover, it is found that the thickness of the threads affects the G_{IR} improvement and that of series C with the thickest thread (88tex) yields the best result. As reported in reference [4, 5], the G_{IR} values increase linearly with increasing stitch density, which is obtained from FEM analysis. In this study, we attempt to use different threads than that used in reference [4, 5]. Our present data indicate that the conclusion of reference [4, 5] has a further validation in spite of being stitched with different threads.

Figure 11. G_{IR} -stitch density plots

Conversion the stitch density to the V_{FT} [5]: Since the stitch density is not influenced by the thread's thickness, the V_{FT} (volume fraction of stitch thread) is introduced here. The V_{FT} is given by the following equation:

$$V_{FT} = \text{Stitch density} \cdot \text{Area of stitch thread} \quad (4)$$

The relationship between the G_{IR} and the V_{FT} is shown in Fig.12. Notice that the slopes of the regression lines in this figure are closer than those in the G_{IR} -stitch density plots in terms of the effect of thread's thickness. And here, the slope of series A (44 tex) and that of series B (66 tex) are

reversed. It is believed to be due to the scatter of the data mainly caused by the difference of the threads' failure. Furthermore, the G_{IR} value and the threads' failure may be influenced by the strength or the thickness of treads, stitching process...etc. In fact, the scatter of data is also investigated in reference [4, 5].

Figure 12. G_{IR} - V_{FT} plots

Typical load-deflection curves for ENF specimens: Typical load-deflection curves for series *a* are shown in Fig. 13(a) and (b). Notice that the specimen with the higher stitch density has the slower crack propagation. This tendency has been obtained from all series of the specimens.

Figure 13. Typical load-deflection curves for (a) an unstitched specimen, (b) a specimen stitched with the density of $0.041/\text{mm}^2$

R-curves for ENF specimens: Figure 14 shows the R-curves for the identical specimens in Fig. 13(a) and (b). First, it is found that the G_{IR} value of (b) keeps on increasing with increasing crack length

and it is not certain whether the value is saturated or not. Therefore, consideration is required for data arrangement and the arithmetic average of two points has been set to the G_{IR} value of (b) in this case. On the other hand, the G_{IR} value of (a) is almost saturated. In such a case, the saturated value has been adapted as the G_{IR} value of the specimen.

Figure 14. R-curves for (a) an unstitched specimen, (b) a specimen stitched with the density of $0.041/\text{mm}^2$

G_{IIR} -stitch density plots: Figure 15 shows the G_{IIR} -stitch density plots for the all series of the specimens. Although it is found that stitching improves the G_{IIR} values slightly, these values are almost constant and are not relative to the stitch density. Moreover, the G_{IIR} improvement of series *c* with the thickest thread (88 tex) does not yield the best one here. However, by nature, it can be predicted that a stitched specimen with the high stitch density and the high thickness of a thread has the larger G_{IIR} value. Considering synthetically, the result of Fig. 15 may caused by the data arrangement. There is a problem in calculating the G_{IIR} value which is not in a steady state, and there may be no reliability in the value. In fact, Mouritz and Jain [7] reported that in stitched composites ENF tests may not be suitable to obtain the G_{IIR} values because a limitation of ENF tests is that crack can only be grown for 25-30mm, which is slightly longer than the length of the stitch bridging zone. In this work, we have been able to obtain only some G_{IIR} data within the maximum crack length. The G_{IIR} values, therefore, may not be in a steady state.

Figure 15. G_{IIR} -stitch density plots

CONCLUSIONS

In this present work, DCB and ENF tests have been conducted for through-thickness stitched CFRP specimens made by RTM process to predict the effect of stitching on the G_{IR} and G_{IIR} . DCB test results have indicated that a specimen with the higher stitch density has the larger area of the strain energy and slower crack propagation in a typical load-COD curve and stitching produces a significant improvement in the G_{IR} value. In addition, it is also concluded that the G_{IR} values increase linearly with increasing stitch density and our present data indicate that the conclusion of reference [4, 5] has a further validation in spite of being stitched with different threads. On the other hand, ENF test results have revealed that ENF tests for stitched composites have a difficulty in calculating the G_{IIR} value which is not in a steady state. The resultant values, therefore, may not be reliable. This warrants future work on the method such as ENC (End Notched Cantilever) test in reference [7] instead of ENF test.

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